

AaWRKY9 contributes to light- and jasmonate-mediated to regulate the biosynthesis of artemisinin in *Artemisia annua*

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Summary

- Artemisinin, isolated from *Artemisia annua* L., is recommended as the preferred drug to fight malaria. Previous research showed that **JA mediated promotion** of artemisinin accumulation was dependent on light. However, the mechanism underlying the interaction of light and JA in the regulation of artemisinin accumulation is still unknown.
- We identified a WRKY transcription factor, AaWRKY9, using transcriptome analysis. The glandular trichome-specific AaWRKY9 positively regulates artemisinin biosynthesis by directly binding to the promoters of *AaDDB2* and *AaGSW1*.
- The key regulator in the light pathway AaHY5 activates the expression of *AaWRKY9* by binding to its promoter. In addition, AaWRKY9 interacts with AaJAZ9, a repressor in the JA signaling pathway. AaJAZ9 represses the transcriptional activation activity of AaWRKY9 in the absence of methyl jasmonate. Notably, in the presence of MeJA, the transcriptional activation activity of AaWRKY9 is increased.
- Taken together, our results reveal a novel molecular mechanism underlying **AaWRKY9 contributes to light- and jasmonate-mediated to regulate the biosynthesis of artemisinin in *A. annua***. Our study provides new insights into the integration of the two signaling pathways to regulate terpene biosynthesis in plant.

Key words: *Artemisia annua*, jasmonate (JA), light signaling, AaWRKY9, artemisinin, glandular trichomes.

33 **Introduction**

34 Malaria is an extremely serious health problem, and caused approximately
35 40,5000 deaths globally in 2018 according to the World Malaria Report 2019
36 (World Health Organization, 2019). Artemisinin Combination Therapies are
37 currently recommended by the World Health Organization as the preferred drug
38 to fight the malaria. Artemisinin, a sesquiterpene lactone, isolated from *A.*
39 *annua*, is extensively used for the treatment of malaria (Greenwood &
40 Mutabingwa, 2002). Considerable efforts have been expended to determine the
41 artemisinin biosynthetic pathway (Fig. S1). The genes encoding enzymes in
42 artemisinin biosynthetic pathway have been isolated. Amorpho-4, 11-diene
43 synthase (ADS), cytochrome P450 monooxygenase (CYP71AV1), cytochrome
44 P450 reductase (CPR), artemisinic aldehyde D-11(13)-double bond reductase
45 (DBR2), an aldehyde dehydrogenase (ALDH1), an alcohol dehydrogenase
46 (ADH1) and cytochrome b5 monooxygenase (CYB5) were involved in the
47 biosynthesis of artemisinic acid (AA) and dihydroartemisinic acid (DHAA)
48 (Bouwmeester *et al.*, 1999; Chang *et al.*, 2000; Zhang *et al.*, 2008; Teoh *et al.*,
49 2009; Paddon *et al.*, 2013). The conversion of DHAA to artemisinin and AA to
50 arteannuin B are regarded as nonenzymatic photo-oxidation reactions (Brown
51 & Sy, 2004, Brown & Sy, 2007). In *A. annua*, artemisinin is synthesized in the
52 glandular trichomes, which contain two stalk cells, two basal cells, and three
53 pairs of secretory cells (Duke *et al.*, 1994; Olsson *et al.*, 2009).

54
55 Although the biosynthetic pathway of artemisinin has been clearly elucidated,
56 the mechanism underlying the transcriptional regulation of the genes in this
57 pathway remains largely unknown. Several transcription factors (TFs) involved
58 in artemisinin biosynthesis have been identified in *A. annua*. For example,
59 APETALA 2/ ETHYLENE RESPONSIVE FACTOR (ERF) proteins, namely
60 AaERF1, AaERF2, AaORA and AaTAR1, have been shown to positively
61 regulate artemisinin biosynthesis by activating the expression of *AaADS*,

62 *AaCYP71AV1* and *AaDBR2* (Yu *et al.*, 2012; Lu *et al.*, 2013; Tan *et al.*, 2015).
63 *AaWRKY1* was also found to increase artemisinin content by activating the
64 expression of *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1* and *AaDBR2* in *AaWRKY1*-
65 overexpression lines (Ma *et al.*, 2009). There is evidence that plant hormones
66 such as jasmonate (JA) also play important roles in artemisinin biosynthesis
67 regulation. For instance, the glandular trichome-specific WRKY TF *AaGSW1*
68 directly binds to W-boxes in the promoters of *AaCYP71AV1* and *AaORA*, and
69 positively regulates their expression, in response to JA (Chen *et al.*, 2016).
70 Similarly, the JA-responsive basic helix-loop-helix TF *AaMYC2* was found to
71 promote artemisinin biosynthesis through direct binding to the G-box of the
72 *AaDBR2* promoter, activating the expression of *AaCYP71AV1* and *AaDBR2*
73 (Qian *et al.*, 2016). In addition, *AaJAZ8*, a repressor in the JA signaling pathway,
74 suppresses the transcriptional activation activity of the *AaTCP14*-*AaORA*
75 complex, which directly binds to and activates the *AaDBR2* and *AaALDH1*
76 promoters; after *AaJAZ8* is degraded by JA treatment, the *AaTCP14*-*AaORA*
77 complex is released, resulting in the enhancement of artemisinin biosynthesis
78 (Ma *et al.*, 2018). Thus, the results from the previous studies show that JA
79 signaling is crucial in the regulation of artemisinin accumulation in *A. annua*.

80

81 Energy from the sun is not only essential for photosynthesis and plant longevity,
82 but also plays significant roles in various development and growth processes
83 (Xing & Quail, 1999). Plants have evolved complex transcriptional networks
84 involved in the response to light and perceive light signals via phytochromes,
85 cryptochromes, phototropins, and UVR8 (Jiao *et al.*, 2007; Rizzini *et al.* 2011).
86 In *A. annua*, overexpression of the blue light receptor cryptochrome1 gene
87 *AtCRY1* from *Arabidopsis* was found to enhance artemisinin production by
88 activating the expression of *FPS*, *ADS* and *CYP71AV1* (Hong *et al.* 2009). In
89 addition, Zhang *et al.* found that both red and blue light signals have the
90 potential to increase artemisinin accumulation by promoting the transcription of

91 artemisinin biosynthetic genes; they found that the artemisinin content was
92 observably higher under red and blue light conditions than under the white light,
93 infrared light, and darkness (Zhang *et al.*, 2018). Previously, we reported that
94 the expression of artemisinin biosynthesis genes significantly decreased under
95 darkness in comparison with light conditions. Transcriptome analysis of *A.*
96 *annua* leaves treated with methyl jasmonate (MeJA) under light or dark
97 conditions showed that light-dependent JA signaling can significantly promote
98 artemisinin biosynthesis (Hao *et al.*, 2017). Recently the bZIP TF ELONGATED
99 HYPOCOTYL 5 (HY5), which is involved in light signaling was found to activate
100 artemisinin biosynthesis by directly binding to the promoter of *AaGSW1* (Hao
101 *et al.*, 2019). However, the mechanism underlying the interaction of light and JA
102 signaling in relation to artemisinin biosynthesis regulation is still unresolved in
103 *A. annua*.

104

105 Here, we demonstrate that *AaWRKY9* plays an important role in regulating
106 artemisinin biosynthesis through the light dependent JA signaling pathway.
107 We found that *AaWRKY9* positively regulated artemisinin accumulation by
108 binding to the promoters of *AaDBR2* and *AaGSW1*. A key TF in the light
109 signaling pathway, *AaHY5*, activated the expression of *AaWRKY9* and bound
110 to its promoter. In addition, the repressor *AaJAZ9* in the JA signaling pathway
111 interacted with *AaWRKY9* and suppressed its transcriptional activation activity.
112 Our results indicate that *AaWRKY9* contributes to light and JA signaling to
113 regulate the biosynthesis of artemisinin in *A. annua*.

114

115 **Materials and methods**

116 **Plant materials**

117 *A. annua* (Huhao1) seeds were harvested from Chongqing, China and bred
118 selectively in Shanghai for several years (Fu *et al.*, 2017). *A. annua* and
119 *Nicotiana benthamiana* plantlets were placed in a greenhouse with a 16h

120 light/8h dark photoperiod at 24°C.
121
122 Light treatments were carried out in an E-30 LED growth chamber (Percival,
123 Boone, IA, USA) with the blue and red light-emitting diode at 22°C. Mean
124 photon flux densities ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) were measured by an Li250 quantum
125 photometer (Li-Cor, Lincoln, NE, USA). Four-week-old *A. annua* seedlings were
126 transferred into the dark, then sampled at 0, 0.5, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 24 hours. *A.*
127 *annua* seedlings pretreated in darkness for 24 hours were exposed to blue or
128 red light with 5, 10 and 40 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD. The leaves were collected after
129 0, 0.5, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 24 hours under blue- (470 nm) or red-light (680 nm)
130 conditions (5, 10, 20, and 40 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD). The leaves were sampled at
131 0, 0.5, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 24 hours under blue- or red-light conditions. For hormone
132 treatments, two-week-old *A. annua* seedlings were treated with 100 μM MeJA,
133 and water with 0.1% of ethanol was used as a mock treatment. The leaves were
134 collected at 0, 0.5, 1.5, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 24 hours after treatment. All samples
135 were separately collected from five seedlings, frozen in liquid nitrogen and
136 stored at -80°C . The cutting seedlings of overexpression and antisense
137 transgenic plants, the control plants transformed with the empty vector, and
138 wild-type *A. annua* plants were cultivated in continuous white light for 2 weeks.
139 Then half of them were transferred to the dark conditions for 24 hours. After the
140 independent pretreatment, the cutting seedlings were sprayed with 100 μM
141 MeJA and 0.1% ethanol (as mock) under the light and dark conditions. The
142 leaves were sampled at 24 and 48 hours for artemisinin analysis. Three
143 biological replicates were performed for each treatment.

144

145 **RNA extraction, transcriptome sequencing and qRT-PCR**

146 Total RNA was extracted from different tissues (young leaves, old leaves, buds,
147 roots, stems, flowers and trichomes) and from leaves at various developmental
148 stages of 5-month-old plants *A. annua* using the RNAprep Pure Plant Kit

149 (Tiangen, Beijing, China) as described previously (Yan *et al.*, 2017, Fu *et al.*,
150 2017, Ma *et al.*, 2018). First-strand cDNA for qRT-PCR was synthesized from
151 the total RNA using the PrimeScript™ RT Master Mix (Takara, Shiga, Japan).
152 cDNA libraries for RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) were constructed from the total
153 RNA of plants treated with blue or red light (40 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD) for 0, 6, and
154 24 hours using the Illumina TruSeq™ RNA Sample Prep Kit (Illumina, San
155 Diego, CA, USA). Subsequently, the cDNA libraries were sequenced at
156 Shanghai Majorbio Bio-pharm Biotechnology Co., Ltd. (Shanghai, China). **The**
157 **raw data was filtered before *de novo* transcriptome assembly. To obtain high**
158 **quality clean reads, the adapter sequences, low-quality or empty reads were**
159 **removed using Trimmomatic (version 0.30). The remaining high-quality clean**
160 **reads were used for *de novo* transcriptome assembly using Trinity software**
161 **(<http://trinityrnaseq.sourceforge.net/>) with the help of the *A. annua* reference**
162 **genome (Shen *et al.*, 2018). All the TF genes and the transcript levels of**
163 **putative genes in different tissues (seed, root, leaf, bud and trichome) were**
164 **identified according to the *A. annua* reference genome (Shen *et al.*, 2018).**
165 **Hierarchical clustering analysis based on RNA-seq data was performed using**
166 **MultiExperiment Viewer software to predict potential TFs involved in the**
167 **biosynthesis of artemisinin.**

168

169 The first leaves of 3-month-old transgenic plants were collected to analyze the
170 expression of *ADS*, *CYP71AV1*, *DBR2*, *ALDH1*, *AaWRKY9*, *AaJAZ9*, *AaORA*,
171 *AaGSW1*, *AaTCP14*, and *AaMYC2*. Real-time qPCR was carried out using the
172 SuperReal PreMix Plus (SYBR Green) Kit (Tiangen, Beijing, China) using β -
173 *ACTIN* of *A. annua* as the reference gene. qRT-PCR assays were performed
174 as previously described (Fu *et al.*, 2017). Three biological repeats were
175 measured for each sample. All the primers used in this study are listed in Table
176 S1.

177

178 **Dual-LUC assays**

179 The effector genes *AaWRKY9*, *AaJAZ9*, and *AaHY5* were inserted into pHB
180 vector. The promoters of *ADS*, *CYP71AV1*, *DBR2*, *ALDH1*, *AaWRKY9*, and
181 *AaGSW1* were cloned into the pGREEN0800-LUC vector as reporters. The
182 empty pHB vector was used as the effector control. The recombinant reporter
183 vectors were transformed separately into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain
184 GV3101 with the plasmid pSoup19, and the recombinant effector vectors were
185 transformed into GV3101. The strains harboring the recombinant vectors were
186 injected into *N. benthamiana* leaves (Voinnet *et al.*, 2003). After incubation for
187 48 hours, the leaves were treated with 50 μ M MeJA for 4 h and water with 0.05%
188 ethanol was used as the control. Equal-sized leaves were collected for dual-
189 LUC assays according to the manufacturer's instructions (Promega, USA). All
190 experiments for each combination were repeated in triplicate. All the primers
191 used in this study are listed in Table S1.

192

193 **Subcellular localization**

194 To determine the subcellular localization of the *AaWRKY9* protein, the yellow
195 fluorescent protein (YFP) was fused to the N-terminal domain of *AaWRKY9*
196 under the control of the CaMV35S promoter. The recombinant plasmid (pHB-
197 YFP-*AaWRKY9*) and the empty vector control were transferred into GV3101,
198 then separately co-transformed into *N. benthamiana* leaves with a strain
199 containing the p19 plasmid (Voinnet *et al.*, 2003). YFP signals were observed
200 by confocal laser microscopy (Leica TCS SP5-II) after 48 hours of incubation.

201

202 **Molecular cloning of promoters and promoter-GUS fusions for**
203 **expression in *A. annua***

204 The promoter sequences of *AaWRKY9* and *AaJAZ9* were predicted using the
205 *A. annua* reference genome (Shen *et al.*, 2018). The predicted promoter
206 regions of *AaWRKY9* (1177 bp) and *AaJAZ9* (1799 bp) were amplified using

207 specific primers, and inserted into the *Bam*HI and *Nco*I sites of pCAMBIA1391.
208 The recombinant plasmids were transformed into *A. tumefaciens* strain
209 EHA105 for *A. annua* plant transformation (Jing *et al.*, 2009). GUS staining was
210 performed as previously described (Ma *et al.*, 2018).

211

212 **Construction and transformation of *A. annua***

213 The full-length coding regions of *AaWRKY9* and *AaJAZ9* were cloned into
214 separate pHB-Flag vectors. To construct the antisense lines, a 500 bp non-
215 conserved domain in the coding region of *AaWRKY9* was cloned into the pHB
216 vector. The constructs (pHB-Flag-*AaWRKY9*, pHB-anti-*AaWRKY9*, and pHB-
217 *AaJAZ9*-Flag) and the pHB vector were transferred into strain EHA105 for *A.*
218 *annua* plant transformation (Jing *et al.*, 2009).

219

220 **Measurement of artemisinin, DHAA, and AA content**

221 Fresh leaves from overexpression, antisense, the transgenic lines transformed
222 with the empty vector and wild type plants were collected, dried at 50°C for 48
223 hours, and ground to powder. Each sample (0.1 g) was extracted twice with 1
224 mL methanol. After centrifuging at 12, 000 rpm for 10 min, the supernatant was
225 collected for the measurement of artemisinin, DHAA, and AA content, as
226 described previously (Jing *et al.*, 2009). All assays were repeated three times.

227

228 **Yeast-one-hybrid and electrophoretic mobility shift assays**

229 The open reading frames of *AaWRKY9* and *AaHY5* were amplified and inserted
230 into the pB42AD vector. Three tandem copies of the W-box motifs in the
231 promoter of *CYP71AV1* (C1-C3), *DBR2* (D1-D7), *ALDH1(A)*, and *AaGSW1*
232 (G1-G4) were cloned into separate pLacZ vectors. Three tandem copies of the
233 G-box motifs in the promoter of *AaWRKY9* were also ligated into the pLacZ
234 vector. The recombinant pB42AD plasmids and pLacZ vectors with the motifs
235 were transferred into the yeast strain EGY48A. The empty vector pB42AD and

236 the motifs were used as the negative controls. The clones were transferred to
237 SD/-Trp/-Ura medium containing X-gal and cultivated at 30°C for two days after
238 selection on the SD/-Trp/-Ura plates.

239

240 The full-length coding sequences of *AaWRKY9* and *AaHY5* were cloned into
241 the pCold-TF vector (Takara, Japan). The recombinant vectors and empty
242 vector were transferred into *E. coli* strain Rosetta (DE3) (TransGen Biotech,
243 China). His fusion protein expression was induced by adding 200 µM isopropyl
244 -d-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) and incubating at 16°C for 14 hours and
245 purified using Ni-NTA (nitrilotriacetic acid) agarose (Invitrogen, USA).
246 Electrophoretic mobility shift assays (EMSA) assays were performed using the
247 LightShift® Chemiluminescent EMSA Kit according to the manufacturer's
248 instructions (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The biotin-labelled W5, W5-
249 mutant, W4, W4-mutant, G and G-mutant probes were synthesized by Sangon
250 (Shanghai, China). All primers are listed in Table S1.

251

252 **Yeast-two-hybrid and pulldown assays**

253 Construction of a cDNA library of *A. annua* for yeast-two-hybrid (Y2H)
254 experiments was carried out by OE BioTech (Shanghai, China) using mRNAs
255 from the youngest leaves and meristem (Yan *et al.*, 2017). The open reading
256 frame of *AaWRKY9* was cloned into the pGBKT7 vector. Y2H screening assays
257 were performed using the Matchmaker Gold Y2H system's user manual (Takara,
258 Japan) as previously described (Ma *et al.*, 2018). For Y2H assays, *AaJAZ9* was
259 inserted into the pGADT7 vector. The combinations of recombinant plasmids
260 were transferred into yeast strain AH109. The positive clones cultivated on SD/-
261 Leu/-Trp agar medium plates were transferred to SD/-Leu/-Trp/-His and SD/-
262 Leu/-Trp/-His/-Ade medium plates. The results were observed after 3 days.

263

264 For pull-down assays, the full-length coding sequence of *AaJAZ9* was cloned

265 into the pGEX4T-1 vector (GE Healthcare), then transformed into *E. coli* strain
266 Rosetta (DE3) to synthesize the GST-AaJAZ9 protein. His-AaWRKY9 protein
267 was produced in *E. coli* strain Rosetta (DE3) harboring the pCold-AaWRKY9
268 plasmid. The pulldown assay was carried out as previously described (Ma *et*
269 *al.*, 2018). All the experiments were repeated three times.

270 **Bimolecular fluorescence and co-immunoprecipitation assays**

271 For bimolecular fluorescence complementation (BiFC) assays, the open
272 reading frame of *AaJAZ9* was cloned into the pxy104 vector, and the full-length
273 coding region of *AaWRKY9* was inserted into the pxy106 vector. The
274 recombinant plasmids (pxy104-*AaJAZ9* and pxy106-*AaWRKY9*) and the empty
275 vectors were transferred into GV3101. Subsequently, combinations of the
276 plasmids were co-transformed into *N. benthamiana* leaves (Voinnet *et al.*, 2003).
277 Confocal laser microscopy (Leica TCS SP5-II) was used to observe the YFP
278 signals.

279

280 For co-immunoprecipitation (CoIP) assays, the open reading frame of *AaJAZ9*
281 was inserted into the pHB-YFP vector. The recombinant plasmids (pHB-Flag-
282 *AaWRKY9* and pHB-*AaJAZ9*-YFP) and the empty vectors were transformed to
283 GV3101. *N. benthamiana* leaves were injected with the combinations of the
284 strains harboring the plasmids. After incubation for 48 hours, the leaves were
285 collected and ground to powder using liquid nitrogen. CoIP assays were carried
286 out as previously described (Ma *et al.*, 2018). For each sample, 15 μ L of Protein
287 G Sepharose (GE Healthcare, UK) and 10 μ L of the rabbit anti-GFP antibody
288 (GenScript, China) were incubated for 2 hours at 4°C. The total proteins from
289 tobacco were added into the Protein G Sepharose, then incubated for 2 hours
290 at 4°C. The proteins were detected using anti-GFP (Abmart, China) and anti-
291 Flag antibody (Sigma-Aldrich, USA).

292

293 **Accession numbers**

294 Sequence data in this article were deposited in the GenBank databases under
295 the following accession numbers: AaORA (JQ797708), AaWRKY9
296 (PWA78774.1), AaWRKY1 (FJ390842.1), AaGSW1 (KX465128.1),
297 AaWRKY75b (KX465129.1), HaWRKY9 (XP_021988131.1), LsWRKY9
298 (XP_023730594.1), CcWRKY9 (XP_024980454.1), AcWRKY9 (PSS02849.1),
299 GhWRKY9 (XP_016719407.1), AtWRKY9 (NP_176982.1), AtWRKY45
300 (NP_186846.1) AtWRKY1 (NP_178565.1), *proADS* (DQ448294),
301 *proCYP71AV1* (FJ870128), *proDBR2* (KC118523.1) and *proALDH1*
302 (KC118525.1).

303 Raw RNA-seq data are available from the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA;
304 accession number: PRJNA669960).

305

306 **Results**

307 **Blue and red light induce the expression of artemisinin biosynthesis** 308 **genes**

309 *A. annua* seedlings cultivated in the light for 2 weeks were transferred to dark
310 conditions for 24 hours. qRT-PCR results showed that the expression levels of
311 the artemisinin biosynthetic genes *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, and
312 *AaALDH1* were significantly reduced after the dark treatment (Fig. S2 a-b),
313 indicating that light plays a critical role in artemisinin biosynthesis in *A. annua*.
314 As demonstrated before, *A. annua* seedlings grown under red and blue light
315 had higher levels of artemisinin and artemisinic acid accumulation in
316 comparison with those grown under white and infrared light (Zhang *et al.*, 2018).
317 Therefore, in this study, red and blue light were used to treat *A. annua* seedlings.
318 The seedlings cultivated in light and pretreated darkness for 24 hours, were
319 transferred to blue light at 5, 10, 20, or 40 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD for 24 hours. qRT-
320 PCR analysis revealed that only the expression of *AaDBR2* was significantly
321 higher compared with the 0 hour under 5 $\text{m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD (Fig. S3 a), and the
322 expression of both *AaCYP71AV1* and *AaDBR2* was significantly increased

323 under $10 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ PPFD (Fig. S3 b). Enhancing the intensity of blue light (20 and
324 $40 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ PPFD) observably increased the transcriptional levels of *AaADS*,
325 *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1* (Fig. S3 c and d). Similarly, the
326 expression of *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1* was
327 significantly higher under 10, 20, and $40 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ PPFD red-light conditions (Fig.
328 S3 f-h), but the transcript levels of these genes did not change when *A. annua*
329 seedlings were exposed to lower intensity red light ($5 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ PPFD) (Fig. S3 e).
330 Overall, these results indicated that blue and red light induce the expression of
331 artemisinin biosynthesis genes in *A. annua*.

332

333 **Identification of blue and red light-induced TF genes involved in** 334 **artemisinin biosynthesis by RNA-seq**

335 To identify light-induced TFs regulating the artemisinin biosynthesis, samples
336 treated with blue and red-light ($40 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ PPFD) treatment for 0, 6, 24
337 hours were used for transcriptome sequencing. The sequencing reads were
338 mapped against the reference genome (Shen *et al.*, 2018). We found that the
339 expression levels of *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1* were
340 significantly higher after seedlings pretreated in the dark for 24 hours were
341 exposed to blue and red light for 6 and 24 hours (Fig. S4 a and b). A total of
342 172 TF genes from the blue-light RNA-seq data and 111 TF genes from the red-
343 light RNA-seq data exhibited expression patterns similar to those of the
344 artemisinin biosynthetic genes.

345

346 To obtain the candidate light-regulated TFs regulating artemisinin biosynthesis,
347 **hierarchical clustering analysis** with the artemisinin biosynthetic genes was
348 performed using the RNA-seq data from different *A. annua* tissues. Thirteen TF
349 genes from the blue-light RNA-seq data and nine TF genes from the red-light
350 RNA-seq data were identified (Fig. S5 a and b) (Shen *et al.*, 2018). Four TF
351 genes (AA532500, AA213240, AA046070, and AA041930) were induced by

352 both blue- and red-light treatments, one of which (AA532500) encoded the
353 AaORA protein, which positively regulates artemisinin biosynthesis by
354 activating the expression of *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, and *AaDBR2* (Lu *et al.*,
355 2013). qRT-PCR analysis confirmed the RNA-seq results, indicating that the
356 expression patterns of 15 candidate genes were consistent with the RNA-seq
357 data (Fig. 1). The transcript levels of the 15 candidate genes in different tissues
358 were further analyzed by qRT-PCR, revealing that 13 genes showed an
359 expression pattern similar to that of *AaORA* (Fig S6). Subsequently, the dual-
360 LUC system was used to identify the function of the candidate TFs related to
361 artemisinin biosynthesis, revealing that an unknown WRKY protein (AA213240)
362 could observably activate the expression of *CYP71AV1*, *DBR2*, and *ALDH1*
363 (Fig. 2). Therefore, AA213240, assigned the name *AaWRKY9*, was chosen for
364 further study. *AaWRKY9* clustered with *HaWRKY9*, *CcWRKY9*, and *LsWRKY9*
365 in a phylogenetic tree (Fig. S7a), and alignment of the *AaWRKY9* protein with
366 several WRKYs showed that *AaWRKY9* contained the conserved WRKY
367 domain (Fig. S7b).

368

369 ***AaWRKY9* is a glandular trichome-specific TF in *A. annua***

370 To investigate the expression pattern of *AaWRKY9*, the expression level of
371 *AaWRKY9* in different tissues and leaves at different developmental stages was
372 analyzed by qRT-PCR. *AaWRKY9* was highly expressed in two types of
373 trichomes and lowly expressed in stems and roots (Fig. 3 a). *AaWRKY9*
374 expression was high in the youngest leaf (leaf 0), and then rapidly decreased
375 with leaf aging (Fig. 3 b), which was similar to the expression pattern observed
376 for the four artemisinin biosynthetic genes.

377

378 To further analyze the expression pattern of *AaWRKY9* in *A. annua*, the
379 promoter of *AaWRKY9* was cloned and inserted into pCAMBIA1391Z carrying
380 a *GUS* reporter gene. Transgenic plants expressing pCAMBIA1391Z-

381 *proAaWRKY9-GUS* were generated. Histochemical GUS staining was only
382 active in glandular trichomes of young leaves (Fig. 3c). GUS activity was not
383 observed in the old leaves from the transgenic plants, nor in the young leaves
384 of wild-type *A. annua*.

385

386 To determine the subcellular localization of AaWRKY9 protein, the yellow
387 fluorescent protein (YFP) was fused to the N-terminal domain of the AaWRKY9
388 under control of the CaMV35S promoter. The YFP-AaWRKY9 fusion protein
389 was exclusively localized in nuclei (Fig. 3d), implying that AaWRKY9 regulates
390 transcription as a TF in nuclei. These results indicate that AaWRKY9 is a
391 glandular trichome-specific TF in *A. annua*.

392

393 **The expression of *AaWRKY9* responds to both light and JA signals**

394 *AaWRKY9* was identified from the RNA-seq data of blue- and red- light treated
395 plants, so we further confirmed the expression pattern of *AaWRKY9* in the dark,
396 and in response to blue- and red-light treatments by qRT-PCR. These results
397 showed that the expression level of *AaWRKY9* was observably reduced after
398 the dark treatment (Fig. 3e), and significantly increased after the blue- and red-
399 light treatments ($40 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD) of plants pretreated with dark conditions
400 for 24 hours (Fig. 3f and g), which have similar expression patterns as those of
401 the artemisinin biosynthetic genes (Fig. S3d and h); these expression patterns
402 are similar to those of the artemisinin biosynthetic genes (Fig. S3d and h),
403 suggesting that the expression of *AaWRKY9* is induced by light.

404

405 Previous research has indicated that artemisinin production is enhanced by
406 treatment with the phytohormone MeJA (Maes *et al.*, 2011). We performed qRT-
407 PCR analysis to check the expression of *AaWRKY9* after MeJA treatment. The
408 results indicated that the transcript level of *AaWRKY9* was significantly induced
409 by MeJA (Fig. 3h). The expression of *AaWRKY9* increased by 1.5 hours after

410 MeJA treatment, peaked at 3 hours, and then decreased (Fig. 3h). Taken
411 together, our results reveal that the expression of *AaWRKY9* increases in
412 response to both light and JA signals.

413

414 **Overexpressing *AaWRKY9* increases artemisinin content and knock-**
415 **down of *AaWRKY9* reduces artemisinin accumulation in *A. annua***

416 To explore the function of *AaWRKY9*, 35S::*AaWRKY9* transgenic *A. annua*
417 lines were generated. Three independent lines (OE-*AaWRKY9*-2, OE-
418 *AaWRKY9*-20 and OE-*AaWRKY9*-28) were chosen for further analysis. The
419 transcript levels of *AaWRKY9* were markedly increased by 2.4-3.5-fold
420 compared with that of wild type (Fig. 4a). The expressions of *AaADS*,
421 *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1* were also significant higher in the
422 *AaWRKY9* overexpression lines (Fig. 4b). HPLC analysis indicated that
423 *AaWRKY9* overexpression transgenic lines produced 1.6-2.2-fold more
424 artemisinin compared with the control (Fig. 4c). In addition, both the DHAA and
425 AA contents were significantly increased in overexpressed transgenic lines (Fig.
426 4c). In addition, when we analyzed the expression of *AaORA* and *AaGSW1*,
427 which encode TFs regulating artemisinin biosynthesis, in the overexpression
428 lines, we found that *AaGSW1* expression was remarkably up-regulated (Fig.
429 4b).

430

431 To further identify the function of *AaWRKY9* in regulating artemisinin production,
432 we downregulated *AaWRKY9* expression in *A. annua* using the antisense
433 vector pCYP71AV1-anti*AaWRKY9* under the control of the glandular trichome-
434 specific promoter *AaCYP71AV1*. We selected three independent lines
435 (anti*AaWRKY9*-8, anti*AaWRKY9*-15 and anti*AaWRKY9*-29) for further analysis.
436 Compared with wild type, the expression of *AaWRKY9* in antisense lines was
437 significantly lower (Fig. 4d). qRT-PCR analysis showed that suppressing the
438 expression of *AaWRKY9* resulted in a decrease in the transcript levels of

439 *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1* (Fig. 4e). Consistent with the
440 down-regulation of artemisinin biosynthetic genes, the contents of artemisinin,
441 DHAA, and AA in the *AaWRKY9* antisense lines were decreased by 35 to 45%,
442 21 to 30% and 40 to 63%, respectively (Fig. 4f). Moreover, the transcript level
443 of *AaGSW1* was down-regulated in *AaWRKY9* antisense lines, compared with
444 wild-type plants (Fig. 4e). We also analyzed the density of **glandular trichomes**
445 in the transgenic plants. The results showed that there was no significant
446 difference in **glandular trichomes** between the transgenic plants and wild-type
447 plants (Fig. S8 and Fig. S9). These results indicate that *AaWRKY9* is a positive
448 TF controlling artemisinin biosynthesis.

449

450 ***AaWRKY9* activates the transcription of *AaDBR2* and *AaGSW1* by binding** 451 **to their promoters**

452 Using dual-LUC assays, we found that *AaWRKY9* could observably activate the
453 promoters of *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2* and *AaALDH1* (Fig. 2). Previous
454 experiments demonstrated that WRKY proteins could specifically bind to the W-
455 box (T)TGAC(C/T) in the promoters of genes (Ma *et al.*, 2009; Eulgem *et al.*,
456 2000; Zheng *et al.*, 2007). Prediction of W-boxes in the promoters of
457 *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1* revealed three W-box fragments (W1,
458 W2 and W3; 1146, 616 and 235 bp upstream of ATG, respectively) in the
459 promoter of *AaCYP71AV1* (Fig. S10a), seven W-box fragments (W1, W2, W3,
460 W4, W5, W6 and W7; 1411, 976, 490, 479, 176, 117, and 20 bp upstream of
461 ATG, respectively) in the promoter of *AaDBR2* (Fig. 5a), and one W-box
462 fragment (W1; 872 bp upstream of ATG) in the promoter of *AaALDH1* (Fig.
463 S10b). To better understand the mechanisms of *AaWRKY9* regulation of the
464 artemisinin accumulation, Y1H assay was carried out. The results indicated that
465 *AaWRKY9* only bound to one of the W-box fragments (W5) in the promoter of
466 *AaDBR2* (Fig. 5b). To further confirm this result, EMSA was performed using
467 the His-*AaWRKY9* protein. This assay demonstrated that His-*AaWRKY9* could

468 bind to the W-box (W5) in the promoter of *AaDBR2* (Fig. 5c). When the His-
469 *AaWRKY9* protein was replaced by His-TF expressed using the pCold empty
470 vector, we could not detect the signal (Fig. 5c). In addition, the band intensity
471 was significantly lower when the mutation was introduced into the W-box (W5)
472 in the *AaDBR2* promoter (Fig. 5c).

473 Because we found that overexpressing *AaWRKY9* increased the expression
474 level of *AaGSW1*, while down-regulating the expression of *AaWRKY9* resulted
475 in a decrease of the transcript level of *AaGSW1* (Fig. 4b and e). To further
476 demonstrate whether *AaWRKY9* could bind to the promoter of *AaGSW1*, the
477 promoter sequence of *AaGSW1* was analyzed, and four W-box fragments (W1,
478 W2, W3 and W4; 1373, 1327, 1181 and 325 bp upstream of ATG, respectively)
479 were identified (Fig. 5d). A Y1H assay indicated that *AaWRKY9* only bound to
480 the W-box (W4) in the promoter of *AaGSW1* (Fig. 5e), and EMSA confirmed
481 that His-*AaWRKY9* directly bound to this W-box (Fig. 5f). In conclusion, **our**
482 **data suggest that** *AaWRKY9* protein positively regulates the artemisinin
483 biosynthesis by directly binding to the W-boxes in the promoters of *DBR2* and
484 *AaGSW1* and activating their expression.

485

486 **AaHY5 enhances the transcription of *AaWRKY9* by directly binding to its** 487 **promoter**

488 HY5 plays an important role in mediating light control of gene expression
489 (Chattopadhyay *et al.*, 1998; Osterlund *et al.*, 2000; Hardtke *et al.*, 2014). In
490 *Arabidopsis*, HY5 interacts with the ubiquitin E3 ligase CONSTITUTIVE
491 PHOTOMORPHOGENIC1 (COP1), and is degraded by COP1 via the 26S
492 proteasome pathway in the dark (Ang *et al.*, 1998). However, under light
493 conditions a decrease in the level of COP1 protein in the nucleus allows for
494 accumulation of HY5. Similarly, *AaHY5* interacts with *AaCOP1* and is also
495 degraded by *AaCOP1* in darkness in *A. annua* (Hao *et al.*, 2019). It was
496 reported that *AaHY5* positively regulates artemisinin biosynthesis by activating

497 the expression of *AaGSW1*. The fact that *AaWRKY9* was identified in the blue-
498 and red-light treatment RNA-seq data, and our finding that its expression was
499 induced by light after the pretreatment in the dark for 24 hours (Fig. 3), indicate
500 that *AaWRKY9* mediates light signals to positively regulate artemisinin
501 biosynthesis. We determined the transcript levels of *AaWRKY9* in *AaHY5*
502 overexpression and RNAi transgenic lines (Hao *et al.*, 2019). The results
503 showed that the expression of *AaWRKY9* was observably increased in *AaHY5*
504 overexpression lines, and significantly decreased in *AaHY5* RNAi lines (Fig. 6a).
505 We found that there were two G-box motifs in the promoter of *AaWRKY9*. To
506 determine whether *AaHY5* controls the expression of *AaWRKY9*, dual-LUC and
507 Y1H assays were performed. The dual-LUC assay demonstrated that *AaHY5*
508 activated the promoter of *AaWRKY9* (Fig. 6b). The EMSA assay indicated that
509 *AaHY5* directly bound to the G-box (CACGTT) in the promoter of *AaWRKY9* *in*
510 *vitro* (Fig. 6c). Therefore, our data indicate that *AaHY5* binds to the promoter of
511 *AaWRKY9* and activates its transcription.

512

513 **The repressor protein AaJAZ9 interacts with AaWRKY9**

514 A previous study showed that JA promotes artemisinin production by activating
515 artemisinin biosynthetic genes (Chen *et al.*, 2016; Shen *et al.*, 2016). Here, we
516 observed that *AaWRKY9* was induced by MeJA (Fig. 3h). To further explore the
517 function of *AaWRKY9* in artemisinin biosynthesis, we performed a Y2H screen
518 using an *A. annua* cDNA library to identify *AaWRKY9* interacting partners. The
519 jasmonate ZIM-domain (JAZ) protein *AaJAZ9* was identified as an interacting
520 protein, and the *AaJAZ9*–*AaWRKY9* interaction was further confirmed by a Y2H
521 assay (Fig. 7a). BiFC and CoIP assays were used to detect the interaction
522 between *AaWRKY9* and *AaJAZ9* *in vivo*. When *AaJAZ9*-nYFP and cYFP-
523 *AaWRKY9* were co-expressed in the leaves of *N. benthamiana*, YFP
524 fluorescence was detected in the nucleus (Fig. 7b). No signal was observed
525 when *AaJAZ9*-nYFP and cYFP or nYFP and cYFP-*AaWRKY9* were transiently

526 co-expressed (Fig. 7b). Consistently with this, a CoIP assay indicated that
527 AaWRKY9 interacted with AaJAZ9 *in vivo* (Fig. 7c). Moreover, a pull-down
528 assay further proved demonstrated that AaWRKY9 interacted with AaJAZ9 (Fig.
529 7d). Taken together, these results demonstrate that AaWRKY9 interacted with
530 the repressor protein AaJAZ9.

531

532 **AaJAZ9 represses the transcriptional activation function of AaWRKY9**

533 JAZs are negative regulators of JA-mediated plant responses (Kazan &
534 Manners, 2012; Qi *et al.*, 2011; Pauwels *et al.*, 2010). In *A. annua*, AaJAZ
535 proteins (AaJAZ1-6, AaJAZ8, and AaJAZ9) were shown to interact with
536 AaMYC2 (Qian *et al.*, 2016; Ma *et al.*, 2018). AaJAZ8 negatively regulates
537 artemisinin biosynthesis by repressing the activity of the AaTCP14-AaORA
538 complex (Ma *et al.*, 2018) and also interacts with AaHD1 to control the
539 development of the glandular trichomes (Yan *et al.*, 2017). qRT-PCR analysis
540 indicated that the expression of AaJAZ9 was highest in trichomes and lowest
541 in shoots (Fig. S11a). In leaves, expression was lowest in the youngest leaf
542 (leaf 0), and slowly increased as the leaves aged (Fig. S11b). In *pAaJAZ9-GUS*
543 transgenic plants, GUS staining was observed in the entire leaf, and strong
544 staining was also observed in the glandular trichomes (Fig. S11c). In addition,
545 the expression of AaJAZ9 was induced by MeJA treatment (Fig. S11d).

546

547 To investigate whether AaJAZ9 represses the function of AaWRKY9 in
548 enhancing artemisinin accumulation, dual-LUC assays were performed. When
549 AaJAZ9 was co-expressed with AaWRKY9 in tobacco, AaJAZ9 reduced the
550 activation of the *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, *AaALDH1*, and *AaGSW1* promoters
551 by AaWRKY9 (Fig. 8). We also used dual-LUC assays to test the transcriptional
552 activation activity of AaWRKY9 in the presence and absence of MeJA. The
553 promoters of *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, *AaALDH1*, and *AaGSW1* were
554 observably activated by AaWRKY9 in the presence of MeJA (Fig. 8). The results

555 also suggested that AaJAZ9 represses the transcriptional activation function of
556 AaWRKY9 in the absence of MeJA. The transcriptional activation activity of
557 AaWRKY9 was significantly enhanced, when AaJAZ9 was degraded by the
558 MeJA treatment. To analyze the role for AaWRKY9 in the interaction of light and
559 JA signaling, the cutting propagations of *AaWRKY9* overexpression, antisense,
560 the empty vector transgenic plants, and wild type *A. annua* plants were
561 cultivated in continuous white light for 2 weeks. Then half of them were
562 transferred to the dark conditions for 24 h. After the independent pretreatment,
563 the cutting seedlings were sprayed with 100 μ M MeJA and 0.1% ethanol (as
564 mock) under the light and dark conditions, respectively. The leaves were
565 sampled at 24 and 48 hours for artemisinin analysis. The results showed that
566 the *AaWRKY9-2* overexpression cutting seedlings accumulated more
567 artemisinin after JA-induced compared with the mock treatment in light (Fig 9
568 a), in contrast, the artemisinin content in *antiWRKY9-15* antisense cutting
569 seedlings after JA-induced showed no obvious change (Fig 9 b). In darkness,
570 we found that artemisinin contents in transformants with empty vector and wild
571 type *A. annua* plants were not obviously increased after sprayed with MeJA at
572 24 and 48 hours (Fig 9 c and d). The artemisinin content was also not obviously
573 promoted in both *AaWRKY9-2* overexpression and *antiWRKY9-15* antisense
574 cutting seedlings at 24 and 48 hours in absence of MeJA compared with the
575 mock treatment (Fig 9 c and d).

576

577 **DISCUSSION**

578 Artemisinin, a sesquiterpene lactone with an endo-peroxide bridge that was
579 isolated from the traditional herbal medicinal plant *A. annua*, **is an effective drug**
580 **for malaria, and artemisinin-based combination therapy is worldwide the first-**
581 **line treatment for falciparum malaria.** The phytohormone JA, which plays crucial
582 roles in regulating plant development, responses to biotic and abiotic stresses,
583 and secondary metabolism (Turner *et al.*, 2002; Maes *et al.*, 2011; De Geyter

584 *et al.*, 2012; Santino *et al.*, 2013; Shen *et al.*, 2016; Ma *et al.*, 2018), has also
585 been shown to **improve** artemisinin content by increasing the expression levels
586 of artemisinin biosynthetic enzyme genes and JA-responsive TF genes (Xiang
587 *et al.*; Wang *et al.*, 2010; Lu *et al.*, 2013; Chen *et al.*, 2016; Qian *et al.*, 2016;
588 Ma *et al.*, 2018). For example, the contents of artemisinin, DHAA, and AA
589 increased 49%, 28% and 80%, respectively, upon MeJA treatment, which
590 increased the density of glandular trichomes and activated the expression of
591 artemisinin biosynthetic genes (Wang *et al.*, 2010). Light plays an important role
592 in the artemisinin biosynthesis (Hao *et al.*, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2018). AaHY5, a
593 light dependent member of bZIP transcription factor, was isolated from *A. annua*.
594 The analysis of *AaHY5* transgenic plants and yeast one-hybrid assays
595 demonstrated that AaHY5 positively regulated the artemisinin biosynthesis by
596 binding to the promotor of *AaGSW1* (Hao *et al.*, 2019). Besides, it was reported
597 that JA increased the artemisinin biosynthesis in a light-dependent manner
598 (Hao *et al.*, 2017). The fact that light and JA play important roles in artemisinin
599 biosynthesis, and that the increase in artemisinin by JA is light dependent,
600 suggest that these pathways interact. **In *Arabidopsis*, COP1 interacts with**
601 **MYB75 to reduce the production of anthocyanin, implying that there were the**
602 **interaction of light and JA signals to regulate anthocyanin biosynthesis (Maier**
603 ***et al.*, 2013). Li *et al.* reported that MeJA promoted anthocyanin biosynthesis**
604 **through increasing the expression levels of DFR, UF3GT, and LDOX under far-**
605 **red light, indicating that MeJA promoted anthocyanin accumulation dependent**
606 **on phyA signaling pathway (Li *et al.*, 2014).**

607

608 In this study, we found that a trichome-specific transcription factor, AaWRKY9,
609 positively regulates artemisinin biosynthesis by directly binding to the
610 promoters of the artemisinin biosynthesis genes *AaDDBR2* and *AaGSW1* (Fig. 4
611 and 5). The contents of artemisinin, DHAA, and AA were observably higher in
612 transgenic *A. annua* lines overexpressing *AaWRKY9* compared with the wild

613 type due to the activation of the expression of *AaADS*, *AaCYP11A1*, *AaDBR2*,
614 and *AaALDH1* (Fig. 4 a, b, and c). In addition, the contents of artemisinin, DHAA,
615 and AA were 35% to 45%, 21% to 30%, and 40% to 63% lower, respectively,
616 in *AaWRKY9* antisense lines compared with wild type (Fig. 4 d and f). We found
617 that *AaWRKY9* was induced by MeJA (Fig. 3h) and that *AaWRKY9* directly
618 interacted with a JA repressor, *AaJAZ9*, in Y2H, BiFC, CoIP, and pull-down
619 assays (Fig. 7). When *AaWRKY9* and *AaJAZ9* were co-expressed, *AaJAZ9*
620 repressed the transcriptional activation activity of *AaWRKY9* (Fig. 8). In the
621 presence of MeJA, the transcriptional activity of *AaWRKY9* was observably
622 increased even when it was co-expressed with *AaJAZ9* (Fig. 8). In addition,
623 qRT-PCR analysis showed that the expression of *AaWRKY9* was observably
624 reduced in dark (Fig. 3 e). In addition, the transcript level of *AaWRKY9* showed
625 a significant increase with the blue and red-light treatment after the
626 pretreatment under the dark condition for 24 hours (Fig. 3 f and g). Dual-LUC
627 and EMSA assays indicated that *AaHY5* activated the transcription of
628 *AaWRKY9* by binding to the G-box motif of *AaWRKY9* promoter (Fig. 6). In
629 conclusion, our findings indicate that that *AaWRKY9* **contributes to light and JA**
630 **signaling** to regulate the biosynthesis of artemisinin in *A. annua* through the
631 following mechanisms: (i) in the dark, *AaHY5* is degraded by the ubiquitin E3
632 ligase *AaCOP1*, leading to decreased transcription of *AaWRKY9*, and in the
633 absence of JA the interaction between *AaJAZ9* and *AaWRKY9* decreases the
634 activation of the *AaDBR2* and *AaGSW1* promoters (Fig. 10 a); (ii) in the
635 presence of JA in the dark, *AaJAZ9* is degraded, but the interaction between
636 *AaHY5* and *AaCOP1* also inhibits the transcription of *AaWRKY9* (Fig. 10 b); (iii)
637 in the light, *AaHY5* increases the transcription of *AaWRKY9*, and *AaJAZ9* is
638 degraded by the JA signaling pathway, resulting in *AaWRKY9* promotion of
639 artemisinin biosynthesis (Fig. 10 c). As mentioned, our results further
640 demonstrate that there is also *AaWRKY9* **contributes to light and JA signaling**
641 to regulate artemisinin biosynthesis in *A. annua*, and also provides a novel

642 molecular mechanism for the interaction of light and JA signals on regulating of
643 secondary metabolism in plants.

644

645 In *A. annua*, several WRKY TFs have been reported to regulate artemisinin
646 biosynthesis, the first of which was AaWRKY1 (Han *et al.*, 2014). Analysis of
647 *AaWRKY1* transgenic plants suggested that AaWRKY1 promotes artemisinin
648 accumulation by activating the expression of *ADS* and *CYP71AV1* (Han *et al.*,
649 2014; Jiang *et al.*, 2016). Subsequently, the WRKY family gene *AaGSW1* was
650 cloned from *A. annua*. AaGSW1 clusters with AtWRKY75 from *Arabidopsis*,
651 and it positively regulates artemisinin biosynthesis by binding to the promoter
652 of *AaCYP71AV1* (Chen *et al.*, 2016). Both *AaWRKY1* and *AaGSW1* are
653 induced by MeJA (Han *et al.*, 2014; Jiang *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2016).
654 However, little is known about the mechanism connecting WRKY TFs with the
655 JA signaling pathway. We suggest that AaWRKY9 and the JA signaling
656 pathway are connected through the repressor AaJAZ9. Together, our findings
657 indicate that WRKY TFs interacted with JAZs to respond JA signaling.

658

659 Several candidate TFs identified from the RNA-seq data could activate
660 artemisinin biosynthesis (Fig. 2). AaORA forms a positive regulator complex
661 with AaTCP14 and promotes artemisinin biosynthesis via the JA signaling
662 pathway (Ma *et al.*, 2018). In this study, the transcription of *AaORA* was also
663 induced by light (Fig. 1). Hao *et al.* found that the expression of *AaORA* was
664 up-regulated in *AaHY5*-overexpression lines, and significantly decreased in
665 *AaHY5*-RNAi lines. However, they did not find a binding site of AaHY5 in the
666 promoter of *AaORA*, demonstrating that *AaORA* might not be activated by
667 AaHY5 (Hao *et al.*, 2019). In addition, we found that the candidate gene
668 AA599040 was also induced by MeJA (Fig. S12). These results indicate that
669 *AaORA* and AA599040 might integrate light and JA signaling to trigger
670 artemisinin biosynthesis through another regulatory network,

671 indicating that artemisinin biosynthesis is regulated by a complex regulatory
672 network. Based on our findings, we also identified some TFs, such as AaORA
673 and AA599040, induced by both light and JA signals. As we mentioned above,
674 AaORA and AA599040 might have other mechanism of regulation artemisinin
675 biosynthesis, and the relation between AaORA or AA599040 and COP1 could
676 be explored in further study. Interestingly, the artemisinin content showed
677 higher in blue- and red-light treatment than those in white light. In agriculture,
678 the strategy of blue- or red-light combined with MeJA treatment might further
679 enhance artemisinin production. Taken together, our study provides new
680 insights into the interaction of different signaling pathways in the regulation of
681 terpene biosynthesis in plants, and also reveal a novel candidate gene for
682 metabolic engineering for enhancement of artemisinin production.

683

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688

689 **Author contributions**

690 K.T. and X.F. designed the research. X.F., B.P., D.H., H.X. and H.L., performed
691 experiments. Y.L., T.C., P.L., Y.T., L.L., J.Z. and X.S. analyzed data. X.F. and
692 B.P. helped to write the manuscript.

693

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841

842 Figure legends:

843 Fig.1 Heatmaps of the expression levels of candidate genes determined by RNA-sequencing
844 and qRT-PCR analysis.

845 Heatmap showing the expression levels of selected transcription factor genes from (a) the blue-
846 light RNA-seq data and (c) the red-light RNA-seq data. Color saturation represents the value
847 of \log_2 RPKM (reads per kilobase per million) for the selected genes. (b and d) qRT-PCR
848 analysis of the selected transcription factor genes from (b) the blue-light RNA-seq data and (d)
849 the red-light RNA-seq data. *ACTIN* was used as an internal control. The expression level of
850 genes at 6 and 24 hours are comparisons relative to the expression level of genes at 0 hour.
851 Data represent the means \pm SD from three technical replicates. **Asterisks denote a significant**
852 **difference of light treatments relative to the 0 h control as determined by a Student's t-test: **,**
853 **P < 0.01; *, P < 0.05.**

854

855 Fig.2 Transcriptional regulation of the selected transcription factors involved in artemisinin
856 biosynthesis. Dual-LUC assay showing the effects of the selected transcription factors on the
857 promoter activation of (a) *AaADS*, (b) *AaCYP71AV1*, (c) *AaDBR2* and (d) *AaALDH1*. The empty
858 vector pHB-YFP was used as the control. The relative LUC activity of the selected TFs are
859 comparisons relative to the LUC/REN ratio of pHB-YFP. Data represent the means \pm SD from
860 three biological replicates. **Asterisks denote a significant difference of the selected TFs relative**
861 **to pHB-YFP as determined by a Student's t-test: **, P < 0.01; *, P < 0.05.**

862

863 Fig.3 Expression pattern and subcellular localization of *AaWRKY9*. (a) Expression levels of
864 *AaWRKY9* in stem, root, old leaf, bud1, bud0, young leaf, shoot and trichome of *A. annua*. Bud0
865 and bud1 were gathered 5 and 12 d after budding. Expression levels of *AaWRKY9* in root, old
866 leaf, bud1, bud0, young leaf, shoot and trichome are comparisons relative to the expression
867 level in stem. (b) Expression levels of *AaWRKY9* in different developmental ages of *A. annua*.
868 Leaf0 (meristem), leaf1 (first leaf below meristem), leaf2, leaf3, leaf5, and leaf7 were collected
869 from the main stem of 5-month-old *A. annua* plants. Expression levels of *AaWRKY9* in leaf1,
870 leaf2, leaf3, leaf5, and leaf7 are comparisons relative to the expression level in leaf0. *ACTIN*
871 was used as an internal control. Data represent the means \pm SD from three biological replicates.
872 (c) GUS staining of *proAaWRKY9-GUS* transgenic *A. annua*. GST, glandular trichome; TST, T-
873 shaped trichome. (d) Subcellular localization of *AaWRKY9*. YFP signal was used as the control.
874 Bar=20 μ m. (e) Relative expression of *AaWRKY9* in the dark. (g and f) Expression levels of
875 *AaWRKY9* in the leaves of *A. annua* exposed to (f) blue light with 40 μ mol m⁻² s⁻¹ PPFD and
876 (g) red light with 40 μ mol m⁻² s⁻¹ PPFD after pretreatment in darkness for 24 hours. White light
877 was used as a mock treatment. (h) Expression level of *AaWRKY9* in the leaf of *A. annua* treated

878 with 100 μ M MeJA; 0.1% ethanol was used as a mock treatment. Relative expressions of
879 *AaWRKY9* at different treating times are comparisons relative to the expression level at 0 h.
880 *ACTIN* was used as an internal control. Data represent the means \pm SD from three biological
881 replicates. Asterisks denote a significant difference of MeJA treatments relative to the 0 h
882 control as determined by a Student's t-test: **, $P < 0.01$; *, $P < 0.05$.

883
884

885 Fig.4 *AaWRKY9* positively regulates artemisinin biosynthesis in *A. annua*. (a and d) Expression
886 levels of *AaWRKY9* in *AaWRKY9* overexpression (a), *AaWRKY9* anti-sense (d), and empty
887 vector (EV) transgenic *A. annua* plants and wild type *A. annua* plants (CK). Expression levels
888 of *AaWRKY9* in transgenic *A. annua* plants are comparisons relative to the expression level of
889 *AaWRKY9* in wild type plant. (b and e) Expression levels of *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*,
890 *AaALDH1*, *AaGSW1* and *AaORA* in *AaWRKY9* overexpression (b), *AaWRKY9* anti-sense (e),
891 empty vector (EV) transgenic *A. annua* and wild type *A. annua* plants. Expression levels of
892 these genes in transgenic *A. annua* plants are comparisons relative to the expression level of
893 these genes in wild type plant. *ACTIN* was used as an internal control. (c and f) The contents
894 of artemisinin, dihydroartemisinic acid (DHAA) and artemisinic acid (AA) in the leaves of
895 *AaWRKY9* overexpression (c), *AaWRKY9* anti-sense (f), and empty vector (EV) transgenic *A.*
896 *annua* plants and wild type *A. annua* plants. All contents are comparisons relative to the
897 contents of wild type *A. annua* plants. Data represent the means \pm SD from three biological
898 replicates. Asterisks denote a significant difference of *AaWRKY9* transgenic lines relative to
899 wild type plant as determined by a Student's t-test: **, $P < 0.01$; *, $P < 0.05$.

900

901 Fig. 5 *AaWRKY9* binds to the promoters of *AaDBR2* and *AaGSW1*. (a and d) Schematic
902 diagrams of the *AaDBR2* and *AaGSW1* promoters. The black lines represent the positions of
903 the potential W box (W1-7) in the *AaDBR2* promoter (a) and the potential W box (W1-4) in the
904 *AaGSW1* promoter (d). The numbers indicate the distance from the translational start site (ATG).
905 (b and e) *AaWRKY9* binds to W-boxes in the promoters of *AaDBR2* and *AaGSW1*. EGY48A
906 yeast expressing pB42AD or pB42AD-*AaWRKY9* and W-box fragments were grown on the SD/-
907 Ura/-Trp medium (20 mg/L X-gal). The blue plaques show protein-DNA interactions. (c and f)
908 EMSA showing *AaWRKY9* binds to W-boxes in the promoters of *AaDBR2* and *AaGSW1*. The
909 His-*AaWRKY9* fusion protein and the labeled probe were used. Unlabeled probe was used as
910 a cold competitor. 10X, 20X, and 40X represent 10-fold, 20-fold, and 40-fold molar excess of
911 unlabeled probe, respectively. His-TF protein was included as a negative control. m: mutated
912 probe.

913

914 Fig. 6 *AaHY5* is a transcriptional activator of *AaWRKY9*. (a) Expression levels of *AaWRKY9* in
915 *AaHY5* overexpression and, *AaHY5* RNAi transgenic *A. annua* and wild type *A. annua* plants
916 (CK). Expression levels of *AaWRKY9* are comparisons relative to the expression level in wild
917 type plant. Values represent the means \pm SD from three biological replicates. Asterisks denote
918 a significant difference of *AaWRKY9* transgenic lines relative to wild type plant as determined
919 by a Student's t-test: **, $P < 0.01$; *, $P < 0.05$. (b) Dual-LUC assay showing that *AaHY5* activates
920 the expression of *AaWRKY9*. The empty vector pHB-YFP was used as the control. The relative
921 LUC activity of *AaHY5* are comparisons relative to that of pHB-YFP. Asterisks denote a

922 significant difference of AaHY5 relative to pHB-YFP as determined by a Student's t-test: **, P <
923 0.01; *, P < 0.05. (c) EMSA showing AaHY5 binds to G-boxes in the promoters of AaWRKY9.
924 The His-AaHY5 fusion protein and the labeled probe were used. Unlabeled probe was used as
925 a cold competitor. 10X, 20X, and 40X represent 10-fold, 20-fold, and 40-fold molar excess of
926 unlabeled probe, respectively. His-TF protein was included as a negative control.

927

928 Fig. 7 AaWRKY9 interacts with AaJAZ9 *in vitro* and *in vivo*. (a) Yeast two-hybrid (Y2H) analysis
929 of AaWRKY9 interaction with AaJAZ9. Transformed yeast cells were grown on control medium
930 (SD/-Trp/-Leu), and selective media (SD/-Trp/-Leu/-His and SD/-Trp/-Leu/-His/-Ade). Pictures
931 were taken after 4 days of incubation at 30°C. Y2H assays were repeated three times, and
932 representative results are shown. (b) Bimolecular fluorescence complementation (BiFC)
933 analysis of the interaction between AaWRKY9 and AaJAZ9 in *N. benthamiana* cells. The N-
934 terminal fragment of YFP was fused to the N-terminus of AaWRKY9 (nYFP-AaWRKY9), and
935 AaJAZ9 was fused to the C-terminal fragment of YFP (AaJAZ9-cYFP). Three independent
936 transfection experiments were performed. Scale bar = 20 µm. (c) Co-immunoprecipitation
937 studies of AaWRKY9 and AaJAZ9 complex formation in *N. benthamiana* leaves. Total protein
938 extracts from *N. benthamiana* leaves infiltrated with constructs harboring FLAG-AaWRKY9
939 and AaJAZ9-YFP were immunoprecipitated with anti-GFP antibody. The co-immunoprecipitated
940 proteins were detected by anti-FLAG antibody. Experiments were repeated three times and
941 similar results were obtained. (d) *In vitro* pull-down assays of AaWRKY9 and AaJAZ9
942 recombinant proteins. His- AaWRKY9 proteins were pulled down with GST-AaJAZ9, and
943 detected on western blots probed with anti-His antibody. Experiments were carried out three
944 times, and representative results are shown.

945

946 Fig.8 AaJAZ9 protein represses the transcriptional activation function of AaWRKY9. (a-d)
947 Activation of the *AaCYP71AV1* (a), *AaDBR2* (b), *AaALDH1* (c) and *AaGSW1* (d) promoters by
948 the AaJAZ9 and AaWRKY9 proteins in the presence and absence of MeJA in *N. benthamiana*
949 leaves. The YFP effector in the mock treatment served as a negative control, and the relative
950 LUC activity of AaJAZ9 and AaWRKY9 proteins are comparisons relative to the YFP controls.
951 The relative LUC activity of AaJAZ9 and AaWRKY9 proteins in the presence of MeJA are
952 comparisons relative to mock treatment. Three independent transfection experiments were
953 performed. Data represent the means ± SD from three biological replicates. Student's t-test: **,
954 P < 0.01; *, P < 0.05.

955

956 Fig.9 Artemisinin content in AaWRKY9 transgenic plants with MeJA treatment in light and
957 darkness.

958 The cutting seedlings of AaWRKY9 overexpression, antisense, the empty vector transgenic
959 plants, and wild type *A. annua* plants were sprayed with 100 µM MeJA and 0.1% ethanol (as
960 mock) in light and darkness. The leaves were sampled for artemisinin analysis at (a) 24 hours
961 and (b) 48 hours in light after MeJA treatment, (c) 24 hours and (d) 48 hours in darkness after
962 MeJA treatment. The error bars represent the means ± SD (standard deviation) from three
963 biological replicates. Asterisks denote a significant difference of MeJA treatment relative to
964 the 0 h control as determined by a Student's t-test: **, P < 0.01; *, P < 0.05.

965

966 Fig. 10 A working model showing that AaWRKY9 contributes to light and JA signaling to regulate
967 the biosynthesis of artemisinin.

968 (a) AaHY5 is degraded by the ubiquitin E3 ligase AaCOP1 to repress the transcription of
969 AaWRKY9 in dark, and AaJAZ9 interacts with AaWRKY9 in the absence of JA. (b) In the
970 darkness, AaJAZ9 is degraded in the presence of JA. But the interaction between AaHY5 and
971 AaCOP1 also inhibits the transcription of AaWRKY9. (c) AaHY5 increases the transcription of
972 AaWRKY9 in the light, and AaJAZ9 is degraded by the JA signal, resulting in promotion of
973 artemisinin biosynthesis by AaWRKY9.

974

975 Supporting Information

976 Additional Supporting Information may be found online in the Supporting Information tab for this
977 article:

978 Fig. S1 The artemisinin biosynthesis pathway in *Artemisia annua*.

979 Fig. S2 Relative expression levels of artemisinin biosynthesis genes (*AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*,
980 *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1*) in light and darkness.

981 Fig. S3 Relative expression levels of artemisinin biosynthesis genes (*AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*,
982 *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1*) in blue and red light (5, 10, 20, and 40 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF).

983 Fig. S4 Heatmap analysis of artemisinin biosynthetic gene expression.

984 Fig. S5 Heatmap of the expression patterns in different tissues of artemisinin biosynthetic genes
985 and transcription factor genes selected from RNA-seq data.

986 Fig. S6 Relative expression levels of the candidate genes in different tissues.

987 Fig. S7 Phylogenetic analysis and alignment of the protein sequences of AaWRKY9 and related
988 proteins.

989 Fig. S8 The trichomes on the adaxial side of mature leaves derived from CK (a), AaWRKY9-20
990 (b), and AntiWRKY9-15 (c) *A. annua* plants.

991 Fig. S9 Density of glandular trichomes on the adaxial side of mature leaves derived from CK,
992 AaWRKY9-20, and AntiWRKY9-15 plants.

993 Fig. S10 Schematic diagrams of the *AaCYP71AV1* and *AaALDH1* promoters.

994 Fig. S11 Expression pattern of AaJAZ9.

995 Fig. S12 Expression levels of AA046070, AA599040, AA075390, and AA574850 in the leaves
996 of *A. annua* treated with 100 μM MeJA.

997 Table S1 Primers used in this study.

998

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(a)

(d)

(b)

(e)

(c)

(f)

(a)

(b)

(c)

New Phytologist Supporting Information

Article title: AaWRKY9 contributes to light- and jasmonate-mediated to regulate the biosynthesis of artemisinin in *Artemisia annua*

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Fig. S1 The artemisinin pathway biosynthesis in *Artemisia annua*. HMGR, 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase. DXS, 1-deoxy-D-xylulose-5-phosphate synthase; DXR, 1-deoxy-D-xylulose 5-phosphate reductase. FPS, farnesyl diphosphate; ADS, amorpha-4,11-diene synthase; CPR, cytochrome P450 reductase; CYP71AV1, cytochrome P450 monooxygenase; DBR2, artemisinic aldehyde D-11(13)-double bond reductase; ALDH1, aldehyde dehydrogenase 1; CYB5 and ADH1, cytochrome b5 monooxygenase and alcohol dehydrogenase.

Fig. S2 Relative expression levels of artemisinin biosynthesis genes *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1* in light and darkness. (a) The seedlings of *A. annua* were transferred from light to darkness. (b) The seedlings of *A. annua* were transferred from darkness to light. The expression level of *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2* and *AaALDH1* are comparisons relative to the expression level at 0 hour. Data represent the means \pm SD from three technical replicates. Asterisks denote a significant difference of the light treatments relative to 0 hour as determined by a Student's t-test: **, $P < 0.01$; *, $P < 0.05$.

Fig. S3 Relative expression levels of artemisinin biosynthesis genes (*AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2*, and *AaALDH1*) in blue and red light (5, 10, 20, and 40 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF). (a-h) The seedlings of *A. annua* were transferred from darkness to (a) blue light (5 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF), (b) blue light (10 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF), (c) blue light (20 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF), (d) blue light (40 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF), (e) red light (5 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF), (f) red light (10 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF), (g) red light (20 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF) and (h) red light (40 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PPF). The expression level of *AaADS*, *AaCYP71AV1*, *AaDBR2* and *AaALDH1* are comparisons relative to the expression level at 0 hour. Data represent the means \pm SD from three technical replicates. Asterisks denote a significant difference of the light treatments relative to 0 hour as determined by a Student's t-test: **, $P < 0.01$; *, $P < 0.05$.

Fig.S4 Heatmap analysis of artemisinin biosynthetic genes. (a) Heatmap showing the expression pattern of the artemisinin biosynthetic genes in blue light RNA-seq data. (b) Heatmap showing the expression pattern of the artemisinin biosynthetic genes in red light RNA-seq data. Color saturation represents the value of \log_2 RPKM (reads per kilobase per million) for the selected genes.

Fig.S5 Heatmap of the expression patterns in different tissues of artemisinin biosynthetic genes and transcription factor genes selected from RNA-seq data. Hierarchical clustering analysis based on RNA-seq data was performed to predict potential transcription factors involved in the biosynthesis of artemisinin. The red box indicated that the candidate transcription factor genes were clustered with artemisinin biosynthetic genes. (a) Heatmap showing the expression pattern of the artemisinin biosynthetic genes and the transcription factor genes selected from blue light RNA-seq data in different tissues. (b) Heatmap showing the expression pattern of the artemisinin biosynthetic genes and the transcription factor genes selected from red light RNA-seq data in different tissues. The distance used for the clustering is based on the Spearman correlation. Color saturation represents the value of \log_2 RPKM (reads per kilobase per million) for the selected genes.

Fig.S6 Relative expression levels of the candidate genes in different tissues. Relative expression levels of (a) *AaORA*, (b) *AA213240*, (c) *AA045620*, (d) *AA574850*, (e) *AA149280*, (f) *AA174100*, (g) *AA046070*, (h) *AA148160*, (i) *AA147030*, (j) *AA247240*, (k) *AA075390*, (l) *AA599040*, (m) *AA333210*, (n) *AA529090* and (o) *AA279750* in different tissues. Relative expression levels of the candidate genes are comparisons relative to the expression level of the candidate genes in root. *ACTIN* was used as an internal control. Data represent the means \pm SD from three technical replicates.

(a)

(b)

Fig.S7 Phylogenetic analysis and alignment of the protein sequences of AaWRKY9 and related proteins. (a) The neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree was constructed using MEGA. Bootstrap values indicate the percentage of 1000 replicates. AaWRKY9 is marked with a black point. (b) Alignment of the amino acid sequences of AaWRKY9 and other WRKY proteins. Identical amino acids are shaded in black. The accession numbers of the sequences shown are as follows: AaWRKY9 (PWA78774.1), AaWRKY1 (FJ390842.1), AaGSW1 (KX465128.1) and AaWRKY75b (KX465129.1) from *Artemisia annua*; HaWRKY9 (XP_021988131.1) from *Helianthus annuus*; LsWRKY9 (XP_023730594.1) from *Lactuca sativa*; CcWRKY9 (XP_024980454.1) from *Cynara cardunculus var. scolymus*; AcWRKY9 (PSS02849.1) from *Actinidia chinensis var. chinensis*; GhWRKY9 (XP_016719407.1) from *Gossypium hirsutum*; AtWRKY9 (NP_176982.1), AtWRKY45 (NP_186846.1) and AtWRKY1 (NP_178565.1) from *Arabidopsis thaliana*.

Fig. S8 The trichomes on the adaxial side of mature leaves derived from CK (a), AaWRKY9-20 (b), and AntiWRKY9-15 (c) *A. annua* plants. Upper images were observed through capturing the yellow autofluorescence of glandular trichome and red autofluorescence of chlorophyll by using fluorescence microscopy. Yellow spots represent glandular trichomes and red backgrounds represent chlorophyll. Bar=500 μ m.

Fig. S9 Density of glandular trichomes on the adaxial side of mature leaves derived from CK, *AaWRKY9-20*, and *AntiWRKY9-15* plants. Data are given as means \pm SD (n = 3).

(a)

(b)

Fig.S10 Schematic diagrams of the *AaCYP71AV1* and *AaALDH1* promoters. The black lines represent the positions of potential W box in *AaCYP71AV1* promoter (a) and potential W box in *AaALDH1* promoter (b). The numbers were shown on the basis of the distance from the translational start site (ATG).

Fig.S11 Expression pattern of *AaJAZ9*. (a) Expression levels of *AaJAZ9* in stem, root, old leaf, bud1, bud0, young leaf, shoot and trichome of *A. annua*. Expression levels of *AaJAZ9* in stem, old leaf, bud1, bud0, young leaf, shoot and trichome are comparisons relative to the expression level in root. (b) Expression levels of *AaJAZ9* in different developmental ages of *A. annua*. Expression levels of *AaJAZ9* in different developmental ages are comparisons relative to the expression level in leaf7. *ACTIN* was used as an internal control. The error bars represent the means \pm SD (standard deviation) from three biological replicates. (c) GUS staining of the *proAaJAZ9-GUS* transgenic *A. annua*. GST, glandular trichome; TST, T-shaped trichome. Bar=50 μ m. (d) Expression level of *AaJAZ9* in the leaf of *A. annua* treated by 100 μ M MeJA. Water was used as mock. Expression level of *AaJAZ9* are comparisons relative to mock treatment. *ACTIN* was used as internal control. The error bars represent the means \pm SD (standard deviation) from three biological replicates. Asterisks denote a significant difference of MeJA treatments relative to 0 hour as determined by a Student's t-test: **, $P < 0.01$; *, $P < 0.05$.

Fig.S12 Expression levels of AA046070, AA599040, AA075390, and AA574850 in the leaves of *A. annua* treated with 100 μ M MeJA. Gene expression levels of (a) AA046070, (b) AA599040, (c) AA075390, and (d) AA574850 in the leaf of *A. annua* treated with 100 μ M MeJA. 0.1% ethanol was used as mock. Expression levels of those genes are comparisons relative to mock treatment. *ACTIN* was used as an internal control. The error bars represent the means \pm SD (standard deviation) from three biological replicates. Asterisks denote a significant difference of MeJA treatments relative to 0 hour as determined by a Student's t-test: **, $P < 0.01$; *, $P < 0.05$.